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ENVIRONMENT PROTECTION THROUGH GOOD CORPORATE GOVERNANCE FOR SUSTAINABLE BUSINESS

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Abstract

Global warming has far reaching impact on all walks of life across the globe. The man made mistakes are the main cause for global temperature is raising which serious issue of concern for world leaders and policy makers. Business and industry has been treated as main culprit responsible for raising temperature where people argue that it is Business and industry are contributories to carbon dioxide, methane and other toxic gases and wastes to environment leading green house formation. There are number of legislative measures both at international and national levels pressurizing business and industry to follow sustainable business policies to protect and preserve the environment. In India, under corporate governance mechanism and CSR philosophy Indian corporate sector is forced to follow environment protection guidelines to have a sustainable business.

Key words: sustainable business, corporate governance, CSR, environment protection, global warming

1. Introduction

The rapid economic, scientific and technological advancements with increasing population have had repercussions on the environment polluting air, water, noise, soil degradation and deforestation. Heavy amount of untreated toxic wastes, poisonous gases are released to environment without treatment. Today everywhere there is hue and cry over the increasing global temperature. And there is increasing public anger on business and industry for their acts of emitting poisonous gases and releasing toxic wastes causing irreparable damage to environment, it is business and industries which are contributing a lot for environment degradation through pollution leading to green house formation which results in global warming, acid rain, droughts and floods. The environment deterioration endangers life of present and future generations. India Inc has a greater role and responsibilities in protecting our mother earth; they have potential strength and resources to go eco friendly operations.

In India Indian corporate sector has taken number of positive measures to protect environment through their green initiatives. In India number of regulations and statutes are there requiring the business houses to go green and adopt eco-friendly operations to protect and preserve the ecology.

2. Corporate governance and environment protection

The triple bottom line principle [TBL] has brought pressure on the corporate sector to address social and environmental issues than concentrating on the monetary gains at the cost of environment and people. The corporate decision and plans have negative impact on environment and should see that such negative impacts would need to be identified, rectified and prevented from recurring.

3. Conceptual clarity

Sustainable business -Adopting those types business strategies and activities that help the business houses meet their own needs along with the needs of its stakeholders today while keeping, protecting, sustaining, developing the human as well as *natural resources and environment* that will be required by people in *future time period*.

Corporate Governance -According to World Bank, Corporate Governance is Blend of law, regulation and appropriate voluntary private sector practices,

- which enables the corporation to attract financial and human capital to perform efficiently, and
- Prepare itself by generating long term economic value for its shareholders,
- While respecting the interests of stakeholders and society as a whole

Environment protection-The protection and improvement of the human environment and the prevention of hazards to human beings, other living creatures, plants and property

Global warming- gradual increase in the average temperature of the Earth's atmosphere and its oceans, a change that is believed to be permanently changing the Earth's climate.

4. Literature review

1. David M. Ong, in his study the author views that internationally agreed environmental principles and nationally applicable environmental liability regimes justify progressive change within corporate governance law. The study views that environmental protection transcended its current place in the external legal framework governing the way companies behave to play a role within the internal regulation of the way companies are run? International trends incorporate environmental liability and environmental management systems are discussed to determine whether environmental considerations should now play a corporate governance role. It is inferred from the review of this study that for the sustainable world development there is a need to integrate the environmental issues with corporate and government decision making and planning process. The corporate decision and plans have negative impact on environment and should see that such negative impacts would need to be identified, rectified and prevented from recurring.

2. Roger Burritt, In this study, the views the management has to adhere to the triple bottom line principle in the corporate governance mechanism. The TBL principle has brought pressure on the corporate sector to address social and environmental issues than concentrating on the monetary gains at the cost of environment and people. The

corporate decision and plans have negative impact on environment and should see that such negative impacts would need to be identified, rectified and prevented from recurring. He views that the companies which responds to the challenges of sustainability can gain competitive edge over other companies through can explore new markets, have greater market share, increase the shareholders value. The author also suggests as to how the corporate environmental Governance be improved.

5. Objective of the study

- ✦ To study the causes of global warming and impact of global warming
- ✦ To study the Corporate Governance mechanism in India requiring environment protection

6. Statement of the problem

The literature review, research findings and what we experience, it is observed that the increasing population with rapid economic, scientific and technological advancements has bad repercussions on the environment polluting air, water, noise, soil degradation and deforestation. The business and industry are releasing heavy amount of untreated toxic wastes, poisonous gases. The corporate decision and plans have negative impact on environment and should see that such negative impacts would need to be identified, rectified and prevented from recurring to protect the environment. In this paper an attempt is made explain as to how the Indian corporate governance mechanism require the Indian corporate sector to protect and preserve the natural resources through sustainable business operations and there by helps to achieve sustainable economic development.

7. Global warming- causes and consequences

Causes of Global warming

The Global Temperature increases due to accumulation of Green house gases leading to green house formation are water Vapour, carbon dioxide, Methane and Ozone. The major causes for green house formation are –

- The main cause for global warming increased accumulation of carbon dioxide in the atmosphere due to burning of Fossil fuels
- Deforestation due to rapid urbanization and industrialization
- Failing sinks in oceans
- Release of Methane into the atmosphere- methane is released during the decay of food, vegetation and paper dumped in landfills. The same thing occurs when sewage wastes break down.
- A increased use of Nitrogen Fertilizers in Farming
- Industries such as cement, liquid natural gas production and coal mining, produce or emit a variety of greenhouse gases.

Consequences of global warming

Raise in global temperature has far reaching and irreparable damage to the environment.

- Increasing global temperatures on the earth by about 3° to 5° C by 2100

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- Rise of sea levels by at least 25 meters (82 feet) by the year 2100 affects coastal regions leading to displacement of people
- Causes acid rain causing severe health problems to human beings and animals
- Raising global temperature Cause crop failures
- Rising global temperature could lead to the extinction of more than a million species.
- Causes severe health problems

8. Corporate Governance mechanism and Environment protection in India

The much of corporate governance law in India and abroad are concerned with how the board room decisions affect the environment and tells the negative impact of board room decisions. Environment protection and pollution prevention are considered to be the essentials of good corporate Governance world over.

In India the legal frame work requiring the Indian corporate sector for effective governance require the corporate to observe and comply with environment protection and green initiatives to be taken care of by India Inc. The important such statutes and regulations are:-

(1) **Green Initiatives in Corporate Governance mechanism** : Green Initiatives in the Corporate Governance - The Ministry has allowed paperless compliances by the companies and Registrar of Companies under the provisions of the Companies Act, 1956- vide :General Circular No:72/2011

(a) Allowing service of Documents including Balance Sheets and Auditors report etc through e-mail addresses-the companies Act has allowed companies to serve of copies of Balance Sheets and Auditors Report etc., to the members through electronic mode to reduce cost of posting and speedy delivery of

(b) Participation by Directors and shareholders in meetings through video conferencing – the companies Act has provided and require the companies to allow the share holders to participate through video conferencing.

(c) Voting in General Meeting of Companies through electronic mode- the Ministry of Corporate Affairs has approved and require Central Depository Services (India) Ltd (CDSL) and National Securities Depositories Limited (NSDL) to provide their electronic platform for capturing accurate electronic voting in General meetings of the company to reduce the use of paper.

(d) Issue of Digital Certificates by Registrar of Companies: the provisions of the Companies Act require the Registrar of Companies has to issue certificates to the companies and other stakeholders in electronic form and under the Digital Signatures of the Registrar of Companies.

(2) Green initiatives under Companies Act, 2013

Schedule VII of the Companies Act, 2013 include and require all companies in India to comply with following green initiatives

- Ensuring environmental sustainability, ecological balance, protection of flora and fauna, animal welfare, agro forestry, conservation of natural resources and maintaining quality of soil, air and water;

- Protection of national heritage, art and culture including restoration of buildings and sites of historical importance and works of art, setting up public libraries, promotion and development of traditional arts and handicrafts

Again these activities constitute CSR activities u/s 135 of the Act and provisions of section 135 require all companies to carry out these green initiatives.

(3) SEBI's Green Initiative requirements under clause 55 of listing agreement

A new Clause 55 shall be inserted to read as under, viz., "Listed entities shall submit, as part of their Annual Reports, **Business Responsibility Reports**, describing the initiatives taken by them from an environmental, social and governance perspective, in the format suggested by the SEBI'. **The Business Responsibility Report** should include. The BRR is envisioned as an annual document describing the measures taken by companies against the nine principles of the NVGs. Principle 6th of the NVGs tells that the Business should respect, protect, and make efforts to restore the environment.

Principle 6: 1. Businesses should utilize natural and manmade resources in an optimal and responsible manner and ensure the sustainability of resources by reducing, reusing, recycling and managing waste.

2. Businesses should take measures to check and prevent pollution. They should assess the environmental damage and bear the cost of pollution abatement with due regard to public interest.

3. Businesses should ensure that benefits arising out of access and commercialization of biological and other natural resources and associated traditional knowledge are shared equitably.

4. Businesses should continuously seek to improve their environmental performance by adopting cleaner production methods, promoting use of energy efficient and environment friendly technologies and use of renewable energy.

5. Businesses should develop Environment Management Systems (EMS) and contingency plans and processes that help them in preventing, mitigating and controlling environmental damages and disasters, which may be caused due to their operations or that of a member of its value chain.

6. Businesses should report their environmental performance, including the assessment of potential environmental risks associated with their operations, to the stakeholders in a fair and transparent manner.

7. Businesses should proactively persuade and support its value chain to adopt sustainable business principle

9. Conclusion

For sustainable world development there is a need to integrate the environmental issues with corporate and government decision making and planning process the corporate decision and plans have negative impact on environment and should see that such negative impacts would need to be identified, rectified and prevented from recurring. All nations should follow Kyoto Protocol, Environmental Accounting in Action, and national governments should make prompt efforts to bring pressure on corporate entities to National governments develop collaborative relationships with industries that produce greenhouse gasses, or industries that manufacture products that result in consumer-generated emissions (cars and trucks, for instance), and assume responsibility for developing and enforcing legislation that facilitate compliance. Or else in the present environmentally conscious society, companies which go green can only survive and prosper and those which refuse to go green definitely perish

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References

- Amrita Nair-Ghaswalla, India Inc goes on green overdrive, Business lines, June 5, 2013
- A Didar Singh, The greening of India Inc, Business lines, November 1, 2015
- Dr.Sanjiv Agarwal, Green Initiatives by India Inc, TaxGuru,7th July,2011
- David M. Ong “The Impact of Environmental Law on Corporate Governance: International and Comparative Perspectives”, EJIL (2001), Vol. 12 No. 4, 685–726
- Piyali Mandal, “Colour me green' is India Inc's mantra this environment day”, Business Standard, 5th June,2012
- Roger Burritt, Corporate Environmental Governance, Australian National University